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PRACTICE-ORIENTED RESEARCH APPROACH IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION PROGRAMMES

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Background and rationale

Political ambitions to stimulate higher education to benefit societal needs has led to fundamental reforms in tertiary education worldwide. In Denmark, education of school and preschool teachers, nurses, welfare professionals and practical engineers has traditionally been undertaken by non-research based educational institutions outside the university sector. The educational reforms undertaken during the last 10-15 years have transformed these institutions into research-based University Colleges (UC) that provide bachelor degree programs within these professional domains. The UC's are supposed to engage in 'applied research' activities that benefit not only education, but are also of value for stakeholders in society in general [1].

The introduction of UC's in Denmark – as a supplement to the traditional universities in providing research – might be taken as a sign of academic drift [2] and the priority of university research and research based teaching by policy-makers.

The bachelor of engineering programmes (BEng) are taught at various UC's and universities in Denmark. Based on the needs of the business sector, the programmes have a research-oriented and a practice-oriented research approach. This secures that businesses will be able to hire engineers possessing practical as well as up-to-date qualifications.

We see that the practice-oriented research approach [3] is conducted in different ways. It is not clearly defined or explained how the approach is enacted and understood in the sector. In some cases, collaboration with companies is done in problem-based and project-based settings where the students learn through work on real life cases with engineering problems[1]. This is one way to conduct practice-oriented research and thereby ensure that the educators are updated in the technical part and use the frameworks of today that the students will be expected to use in

their future job (in the companies) [4] These differences make it difficult to compare different courses and educations.

The purpose for this workshop is to discuss how practice-oriented research approach could be defined and to share ideas and experiences about how it is incorporated into courses and education programmes at different higher educational institutions. Each way of incorporation will be discussed in relation to effect, strengths and challenges. The focus will be on bachelor of engineering programmes. The main target group for this workshop is all teachers and educational consultants who have an interest in the topic. But others are also welcome to participate as we would like to have a broad discussion.

Workshop session

Introduction (5 minutes) (zoom) link will be sent out to the participants

The authors will set the scene by introducing the questions for discussion and describe why this is relevant and which dilemmas they see. The program for the workshop session will be explained including what the participants are expected to do and learn from the workshop.

Hands-on session (25 minutes)(break out rooms zoom)

The next step will be a hands-on session. The workshop authors will facilitate the session. The authors will mix the participants randomly and create “break out rooms” in zoom for each group.

Each group will discuss the following two questions and write some notes from the discussions. The authors will hand out some keywords for each question to start the discussion

- How can practice-oriented research approaches in engineering education be defined?
- How are practice-oriented research approaches incorporated into courses/educational programmes?
 - o Effects?
 - o Strengths?
 - o Challenges?

At the end of the session, the participants leave the break out rooms and return to the main room. Each group will give a very brief presentation of their findings. The other participants will be invited to comment on these findings and the facilitators will facilitate the process. At the end of the session, the facilitators will summarize the discussion.

Discussion and conclusion (10 minutes) zoom

In the last part of the session, the participants will discuss the result of the hands-on activity and reflect on the process including feedback on the session.

Expected outcomes/results

At the workshop, the participants will discuss various definitions and approaches, and the expected outcome from the workshop is a broader understanding of practice-oriented research approaches and their use.

The authors will collect the conclusions from the workshop session and these will be included in the final conference proceeding.

How is this work significant for Engineering Education

Having a common understanding about the definition of practice-oriented research can be significant in order to enhance engineering education in general. It offers a common language to educators to incorporate relevant research into education programmes and strengthen the ability of students to apply practice-oriented research into practical challenges.

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